

РАЗДЕЛ. МЕДИЦИНСКИЕ НАУКИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4567820>

УДК 618.33

**COMMUNICATION BETWEEN THE URBANIZATION AND
INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGION WITH THE NUMBER
OF THE BORN PREMATURE CHILDREN**

A.S. Aleksandrovich,

PhD in Medical sciences

T.I. Zimatkina,

PhD in Biological sciences, Associate Professor,

Grodno state medical university,

Republic of Belarus, Grodno

Abstract: The interrelation between the numbers of the born premature children in a certain region with number of the registered industrial enterprises is studied. It is established that in territories with the greatest number of the industrial enterprises higher level of the birth of premature children is observed. Proceeding from it, women are recommended to bear whenever possible the child far from brisk city life.

Keywords: pregnancy, newborns, prematurity, urbanization, industrial enterprises

**СВЯЗЬ МЕЖДУ УРБАНИЗАЦИЕЙ И ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫМ
РАЗВИТИЕМ РЕГИОНА С КОЛИЧЕСТВОМ РОЖДЕННЫХ
НЕДОНОШЕННЫХ ДЕТЕЙ**

А.С. Александрович,

к.м.н.

Т.И. Зиматкина,

к.б.н., доц.,

Гродненский государственный медицинский университет,

Республика Беларусь, г. Гродно

Аннотация: Изучена взаимосвязь между количеством рождённых недоношенных детей в определённом регионе с числом зарегистрированных промышленных предприятий. Установлено, что на территориях с наибольшим количеством промышленных предприятий наблюдается более

высокий уровень рождения недоношенных детей. Исходя из этого, женщинам рекомендуется по возможности вынашивать ребенка вдали от оживленной городской жизни.

Ключевые слова: беременность, новорожденные, недоношенность, урбанизация, промышленные предприятия

Relevance: According to world statistics, every tenth child is born premature, that in figures makes 8-13 million babies [1-3].

Among 10 countries with the highest rates of premature children, along with the African, the USA and Brazil are.

The lowest interest – in Belarus, Ecuador, Latvia, Lithuania, Estonia, Finland and Japan.

Despite it, in our country, as well as around the world, growth of cases of the premature birth of babies is observed [4-6].

According to data of National Statistical Committee of Republic of Belarus for 2009-2013, the number of the born children for this period was 109268 people (2009), 108 032 (2010 year), 109203 (2011 year), 116094 (2012 year) and 118291 persons (2013).

The number of the born premature children was 4614 (2009), 4569 (2010), 4768 (2011), 5210 (2012) and 5155 (2013).

The number given rise premature in % to number been born live averages 4.4 % in spite of the fact that every year the number of the born premature children grows [7, 8].

Purpose: To establish interrelation between the number of the born premature children in a certain region with number of the registered industrial enterprises

Materials and methods of a research: for achievement of a goal, studying of data of National Statistical committee of RB and data of the official statistical collection of the Ministry of Health of RB is carried out; methods of comparative analysis, generalization and systematization and a statistical method of a research are used.

Results and their discussions: distinguish four degrees of prematurity of newborn children according to body weight in grams:

- the 1st degree of 2001-2500;
- the 2nd degree of 1501-2000;
- the 3rd degree of 1001-1500;
- the 4th degree of 1000 and less – «extremely premature».

If thirty flyings ago the newborn child of the fourth degree of prematurity, weighing 500 grams was doomed, then today he has high chance to survive.

Weight of a condition of the newborn is defined by degree of prematurity and his functional immaturity: whether he is capable to maintain constant body temperature whether it has sucking and deglutitory reflexes, whether there are at it short-term apnoeas and attacks of cyanosis (cyanosis), whether the hypomyotonia, poverty of motor and emotional reactions is expressed.

According to literature, the basic the factors influencing premature births are:

1. Social and economic factors.
2. Social and biological factors.
3. Various diseases.

One of essential factors, which is capable to cause premature births, is the high level of environmental pollution by production wastes.

Concentration of modern industrial production and scales of its activity in many cases are followed by receipt to the environment of such amount of pollutants and xenobiotics, which cannot be neutralized by natural factors. Besides, in process of saturation of the biosphere these or those production wastes the potential of its neutralized abilities gradually falls. In this regard, environmental pollution (first of all, water and air) led to forming of new biogeochemical structures of the regions which are characterized by excess accumulation of harmful substances and negative impact on health of the population.

Pollution of atmospheric air is the most serious environmental problem of the modern city, it causes significant damage to health of citizens. In the atmosphere there is a huge amount of harmful substances (carbon dioxide, hydrogen sulfide, ethylene, sulfur oxide, butylene, chrome, etc.) which get to an organism of mother and are transferred to a fruit. Air pollution level directly depends on emissions of the industrial enterprises. At high extent of pollution, the risk of premature births increases. And as most the industrial enterprises is concentrated in the cities, concentration of harmful substances in air in these territories is higher, and, therefore, the risk of premature births considerably increases. Impact of harmful emissions on a female body is especially dangerous during the third trimester of pregnancy.

Proceeding from data of National Statistical committee of RB for 2015, all on the Republic 13,126 organizations of the industry are registered. The greatest number is in Minsk (3760), the Minsk region (2889), least of all enterprises – in the Vitebsk and Grodno regions (1111 and 1200 respectively). In the Brest region 1551 industrial organizations, in Gomel and Mogilev-1369 and 1246 respectively. It allows judging that in these territories to a greater or lesser extent the organism of the pregnant woman is exposed to negative impact of harmful substances.

The number of the children born premature been born live for 2015 (119,028 people) is of total number: 5.7 % in Minsk, 3.5 % in the Minsk region,

4.5 % in the Gomel, 4.4 % in the Vitebsk, 4.2 % in the Mogilev, 3.2 % in the Brest and 2.8 % in Grodno areas.

Conclusion: thus, having analyzed and having studied statistical data on industrial development of various regions of Republic of Belarus and the number of premature birth in the respective regions, it is possible to say that in territories with the greatest number of the registered enterprises of the industry the highest level of the birth of premature children is observed. Proceeding from it, women are recommended to bear whenever possible the child far from brisk city life.

References

- [1] Zaitsev G.K. Valeology. Health culture. / G.K. Zaitsev, A.G. Zaitsev. – Samara: Publishing house «BAHRAKH-M», 2003. 272 p.
- [2] Health care in the Republic of Belarus: official. stat. Sat. for 2016. – Minsk: GU RNMB, 2017. 277 p.
- [3] Zimatkina T.I. Valeology: textbook. Allowance. / T.I. Zimatkina, A.S. Alexandrovich. – Grodno: GRSMU, 2020. 296 p.
- [4] Stozharov A.N. Medical ecology: teaching method. Manual. / A.N. Stozharov. – Minsk: Higher. shk., 2007. 368 p.
- [5] Bodyazhin V.I. Obstetrics. / V.I. Bodyazhin, K.N. Zhmakin, A.P. Kiryushchenkov. – Educational literature for students of medical institutes, 1986. 33-35 pp.
- [6] Women's health. Great Medical Encyclopedia. // Great Popular Medical Encyclopedia. – Moscow: «Eksmo», 2010. 862-863 pp.
- [7] Bondarenko N.A. Questions of modern pediatrics. / N.A. Bondarenko. – 2005. Iss. 1. vol. 4. 4 p.
- [8] Balakhonov A.V. Development errors. Ed. 2nd, revised. and supplemented. / A.V. Balakhonov. – SPb.: «ELBI-SPb». 2001. 288 p.

Bibliography (Transliterated)

- [1] Zaitsev G.K. Valeology. Health culture. / G.K. Zaitsev, A.G. Zaitsev. - Samara: Publishing house "BAHRAKH-M", 2003. 272 p.
- [2] Health care in the Republic of Belarus: official. stat. Sat. for 2016. - Minsk: GU RNMB, 2017.277 p.
- [3] Zimatkina T.I. Valeology: textbook. Allowance. / T.I. Zimatkina, A.S. Alexandrovich. - Grodno: GRSMU, 2020.296 p.
- [4] Stozharov A.N. Medical ecology: teaching method. Manual. / A.N. Stozharov. - Minsk: Higher. shk., 2007.368 p.

[5] Bodyazhin V.I. Obstetrics. / V.I. Bodyazhin, K.N. Zhmakin, A.P. Kiryushchenkov. - Educational literature for students of medical institutes, 1986.33-35 pp.

[6] Women's health. Great Medical Encyclopedia. // Great Popular Medical Encyclopedia. - Moscow: "Eksmo", 2010. 862-863 pp.

[7] Bondarenko N.A. Questions of modern pediatrics. / N.A. Bondarenko. - 2005. Iss. 1.vol. 4.4 p.

[8] Balakhonov A.V. Development errors. Ed. 2nd, revised. and supplemented. / A.V. Balakhonov. - SPb .: "ELBI-SPb". 2001.288 p.

© A.S. Aleksandrovich, T.I. Zimatkina, 2021

Поступила в редакцию 16.01.2021

Принята к публикации 15.01.2021

Для цитирования:

Aleksandrovich A.S., Zimatkina T.I. Communication between the urbanization and industrial development of the region with the number of the born premature children // Инновационные научные исследования : сетевой журнал. 2021. № 1-2(3). С. 137-141. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>